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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF BOSENTAN
SUSTAINED RELEASE TABLETS**Rithu Raj G^{1*} and Silas P²¹Department of Pharmaceutics, University College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Palamuru University, Bandameedipally, Mahabubnagar-509001.

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Abstract:

The aim of the present study was to develop sustained release formulation of Bosentan to maintain constant therapeutic levels of the drug for over 8 hrs. Various synthetic polymers were employed as polymers. Bosentan dose was fixed as 62.5 mg. Total weight of the tablet was considered as 200 mg. Polymers were used in the concentration of 31.5, 41.25, 62.5 mg concentration. All the formulations were passed various physicochemical evaluation parameters and they were found to be within limits. And the drug and excipient compatibility studies showed that there is no interaction between the drug and polymers employed in the formulation. Whereas from the dissolution studies it was evident that the formulation F3, showed better and desired drug release pattern i.e., 98.13 respectively % in 8 hours.

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INTRODUCTION:

Hypertension, or high blood pressure, is a chronic condition characterized by elevated arterial pressure, measured as systolic and diastolic pressures. Normal blood pressure ranges from 100–140 mmHg systolic and 60–90 mmHg diastolic, with hypertension defined as consistently $\geq 140/90$ mmHg. It is typically asymptomatic initially but poses significant risks for heart disease, stroke, aneurysms, and kidney disease. Hypertension is classified as primary (essential), with no clear cause, or secondary, resulting from identifiable conditions like kidney disease or

endocrine disorders. Primary hypertension involves complex interactions between genetics and environmental factors such as high salt intake, obesity, and stress. Secondary hypertension can arise from conditions like Cushing's syndrome or medications. Pathophysiologically, hypertension is often due to increased peripheral resistance, with potential contributions from structural changes in blood vessels, endothelial dysfunction, and sympathetic nervous system abnormalities. Aging, obesity, and certain inflammatory markers also play roles in its development.

Instruments used:**Table 1**

S.No.	Instrument name	Manufacturer	Model
1	UV spectrophotometer	Lab India	Uv-3000
2	Rotary punching machine	karnavati	Rimek minipress-II
3	Weighing balance	WENSAR	Apx224
4	Digital vernier calipers	Mitutoyo ,japan	Dg-0.1-150
5	P ^H meter	Lab India	SAB 5000
6	Roche Friabilator	Labindia, Mumbai, India	FT-1020
7	DissolutionApparatus	Labindia, Mumbai, India	Ds-8000
8	Hardness tester	Sisco, Mumbai, India.	Sisco(monsanto type)
9	FTIR	Brucker	Alpha-T

CHEMICALS USED**Table 2**

S.No.	Materials	Purpose	Source
1	Bosentan	Drug	Natco pharma pvt ltd
2	Eudragit RSPO	Polymer	SD Fine-Chem. Pvt., Mumbai, India.
3	Chitosan	Polymer	SD Fine-Chem. Pvt., Mumbai, India.
4	Magnesium Stearate	Glident	Dr. Reddy's Laboratories, Hyderabad, AP.
5	Aerosol	Lubricant	Merk laboratories, Mumbai
6	Micro Crystalline Cellulose	Diluent	SD Fine-Chem. Pvt., Mumbai, India.

METHODOLOGY:**Analytical method development:****Preparation of 0.1N HCl (pH 1.2):**

Take 8.5ml of HCl in a measuring cylinder and transfer it into a beaker containing 1000 ml of distilled water carefully and stir it thoroughly it gives us 0.1N HCl.

Preparation of 6.8 Phosphate Buffer:

Take 6.8 grams of KH_2PO_4 (potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate) and add it to 1000 ml of distilled water and stir well until the solid content dissolves completely.

Take 0.896 grams of sodium hydroxide pellets and add them to 100 ml of distilled water and stir well until the solid content completely dissolves. Add this solution to the above solution drop by drop until the desired pH is obtained.

a) Determination of Absorption Maxima:

A solution containing the concentration 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ drug was prepared in 0.1N HCl and pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer UV spectrums were taken using a Double beam UV/VIS spectrophotometer.

The solution was scanned in the range of 200 – 400.

b) Preparation Calibration Curve:

100mg of Bosentan pure drug was dissolved in 100ml of Methanol (stock solution) 10 ml of above solution was taken and make up with 100ml by using 0.1 N HCl (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$). From this 10ml was taken and make up with 100 ml of 0.1 N HCl (10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$). The above solution was subsequently diluted with 0.1N HCl to obtain a series of dilutions Containing 0.5,0.10,0.15,0.20,0.25,0.30,0.35 and 0.40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of Bosentan per ml of solution. The absorbance of the above dilutions was measured at 242 nm by using UV-Spectrophotometer taking 0.1N HCl as blank. Then a graph was plotted by taking Concentration on X-Axis and Absorbance on Y-Axis which gives a straight line Linearity of standard curve was assessed from the square of correlation coefficient (R^2) which is determined by least-square linear regression analysis. The above procedure was repeated by using pH 6.8 phosphate buffer solutions.

Construction of Bosentan Calibration Curve with Phosphate Buffer Ph 6.8:

100mg of Bosentan was dissolved in 100ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 to give a concentration of 1mg/ml (1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$). From the above standard

$$\tan \theta = h / r \quad \tan \theta = \text{Angle of repose}$$

$$h = \text{Height of the cone ,}$$

solution (1000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) 10 ml was taken and diluted to 100ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8 to give a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$. From this stock solution aliquots of 0.2,0.4,0.6,0.8 and 1 ml were pipette out in 10 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up to the mark with phosphate buffer PH 6.8 to produce concentration of 2,4,6,8 and 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ respectively. The absorbance (abs) of each conc. was measured at respective (λ_{max}) i.e., 244 nm.

Drug – Excipient Compatibility Studies**Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy:**

The physical properties of the physical mixture were compared with those of plain drugs. Samples were mixed thoroughly with 100mg potassium bromide IR powder and compacted under vacuum at a pressure of about 12 psi for 3 minutes. The resultant disc was mounted in a suitable holder in Perkin Elmer IR spectrophotometer and the IR spectrum was recorded from 3500 cm^{-1} to 500 cm^{-1} . The resultant spectrum was compared for any spectrum changes.

Preformulation Parameters

The quality of tablets, once formulated by rule, is generally dictated by the quality of physicochemical properties of blends. There are many formulations and process variables involved in mixing and all these can affect the characteristics of blends produced. The various characteristics of blends tested as per Pharmacopoeia.

Angle Of Repose:

The frictional force in a loose powder can be measured by the angle of repose. It is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of the pile of the powder and the horizontal plane. If more powder is added to the pile, it slides down the sides of the pile until the mutual friction of the particles producing a surface angle, is in equilibrium with the gravitational force. The fixed funnel method was employed to measure the angle of repose. A funnel was secured with its tip at a given height (h), above a graph paper that is placed on a flat horizontal surface. The blend was carefully poured through the funnel until the apex of the conical pile just touches the tip of the funnel. The radius (r) of the base of the conical pile was measured. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula:

$$r = \text{Radius of the cone base}$$

Table 3: Angle of Repose values (as per USP)

Angle of Repose	Nature of Flow
<25	Excellent
25-30	Good
30-40	Passable
>40	Very poor

Bulk Density:

Density is defined as weight per unit volume. Bulk density is defined as the mass of the powder divided by the bulk volume and is expressed as gm/cm³. The bulk density of a powder primarily depends on particle size distribution, particle shape and the tendency of particles to adhere together. Bulk density is very important in the size of containers needed for handling, shipping, and storage of raw material and blend. It is also important in size blending equipment.

10 gm powder blend was sieved and introduced into a dry 20 ml cylinder, without compacting. The powder was carefully leveled without compacting and the unsettled apparent volume, (V_o), was read. The bulk density was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Bulk Density} = M / V_o$$

Where, M = weight of sample
V_o = apparent volume of powder

Tapped Density:

After carrying out the procedure as given in the measurement of bulk density the cylinder containing the sample was tapped using a suitable mechanical tapped density tester that provides 100 drops per minute and this was repeated until the difference between succeeding measurement is less than 2 % and then tapped volume, V measured, to the nearest

graduated unit. The tapped density was calculated, in gm per L, using the formula:

$$\text{Tap} = M / V$$

Where, Tap= Tapped Density
M = Weight of sample
V= Tapped volume of powder

Measures of Powder Compressibility:

The Compressibility Index (Carr's Index) is a measure of the propensity of a powder to be compressed. It is determined from the bulk and tapped densities. In theory, the less compressible a material the more flowable it is. As such, it is a measure of the relative importance of interparticle interactions. In a free-flowing powder, such interactions are generally less significant, and the bulk and tapped densities will be closer in value.

For poorer flowing materials, there are frequently greater interparticle interactions, and a greater difference between the bulk and tapped densities will be observed. These differences are reflected in the Compressibility Index which is calculated using the following formulas:

$$\text{Carr's Index} = [(\text{tap} - b) / \text{tap}] \times 100$$

Where, b = Bulk Density
Tap = Tapped Density

Table 4: Carr's index value (as per USP)

Carr's index	Properties
5 – 15	Excellent
12 – 16	Good
18 – 21	Fair to Passable
2 – 35	Poor
33 – 38	Very Poor
>40	Very Very Poor

Formulation Development of Tablets:

All the formulations were prepared by direct compression. The compositions of different formulations are given in Table 6.3. The tablets were prepared as per the procedure given below and aim is to prolong the release of Bosentan. Total weight of the tablet was considered as 200mg.

Procedure:

- 1) Bosentan and all other ingredients were individually passed through sieve no \neq 60.
- 2) All the ingredients were mixed thoroughly by triturating up to 15 min.
- 3) The powder mixture was lubricated with aerosol.
- 4) The tablets were prepared by using a direct compression method.

Table 5: Formulation composition for tablets F1-F9.

Excipients	Drug	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Bosentan(mg)		62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5
Eudragit-RSPO(mg)		31.25	41.65	62.5	0	0	0	0	0	0
EudragitS100(mg)		0	0	0	31.25	41.65	62.5	0	0	0
EudragitL100(mg)		0	0	0	0	0	0	31.25	41.65	62.5
Mag.stearate(mg)		5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Aerosol		5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
MCC		96.25	85.85	65	96.25	65	85.85	96.25	85.85	65
TOTAL		200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

All the quantities were in mg for a total weight of 200mg.

Evaluation Of Post Compression Parameters For Prepared Tablets

The designed formulation tablets were studied for their physicochemical properties like weight variation, hardness, thickness, friability and drug content.

Weight Variation Test:

To study the weight variation, twenty tablets were taken and their weight was determined individually and collectively on a digital weighing balance. The average weight of one tablet was determined from

the collective weight. The weight variation test would be a satisfactory method of determining the drug content uniformity. Not more than two of the individual weights deviate from the average weight by more than the percentage shown in the following table and none deviate by more than twice the percentage. The mean and deviation were determined. The percent deviation was calculated using the following formula.

$$\% \text{ Deviation} = \left(\frac{\text{Individual weight} - \text{Average weight}}{\text{Average weight}} \right) \times 100$$

Table 6: Pharmacopoeial specifications for tablet weight variation

Average weight of tablet (mg) (I.P)	Average weight of tablet (mg) (U.S.P)	Maximum percentage difference allowed
Less than 80	Less than 130	± 10
80-250	130-324	± 7.5
More than	More than 324	± 5

Hardness:

Hardness of tablet is defined as the force applied across the diameter of the tablet in order to break the tablet. The resistance of the tablet to chipping, abrasion or breakage under condition of storage transformation and handling before usage depends on its hardness. For each formulation, the hardness of three tablets was determined using Monsanto hardness tester and the average is calculated and presented with deviation.

Thickness:

Tablet thickness is an important characteristic in reproducing appearance. Tablet thickness is an important characteristic in reproducing appearance. Average thickness for core and coated tablets is calculated and presented with deviation.

Friability:

It measures the mechanical strength of tablets. Roche friabilator was used to determine the friability by following procedure. Prewedged tablets were placed

in the friabilator. The tablets were rotated at 25 rpm for 4 minutes (100 rotations). At the end of test, the tablets were re weighed, loss in the weight of tablet is the measure of friability and is expressed in percentage as

$$\% \text{ Friability} = [(W1 - W2) / W1] \times 100$$

Where, W1 = Initial weight of three tablets
W2 = Weight of the three tablets after testing

Determination Of Drug Content:

Tablets were tested for their drug content. Ten tablets were finely powdered quantities of the powder equivalent to one tablet weight of Bosentan were accurately weighed, transferred to a 100 ml volumetric flask containing 50 ml water and were allowed to stand to ensure complete solubility of the drug. The mixture was made up to volume with water. The solution was suitably diluted and the absorption was determined by UV –Visible spectrophotometer. The drug concentration was calculated from the calibration curve.

Note :the regression value for Bosentan from the standard graph is.

$$\text{Absorbance} - \text{Intercept}$$

$$\text{Concentration (mcg/ml)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance} - \text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}}$$

$$\text{Slope}$$

$$\text{Drug content (mg)} = \text{concentration} \times \text{dilution factor}$$

$$\text{Drug content (mg)}$$

<i>In vitro</i> drug release studies Parameters:	%drug content =	Label claim(mg)
Apparatus	--	USP-II, Paddle Method
Dissolution Medium	--	0.1 N HCl, p H 6.8 Phosphate buffer
RPM	--	50
Sampling intervals (hrs)	--	0.5,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8.
Temperature	--	37°C± 0.5°C.

Procedure:

900ml of 0.1 HCl was placed in the vessel and the USP apparatus –II (Paddle Method) was assembled. The medium was allowed to equilibrate to temp of $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. Tablet was placed in the vessel and the vessel was covered the apparatus was operated for 2 hours and then the medium 0.1 N HCl was removed and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was added process was continued from upto 12 hrs at 50 rpm. At definite time intervals of 5 ml of the receptors fluid was withdrawn, filtered and again 5ml receptor fluid was replaced. Suitable dilutions were done with receptor fluid and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 242 and 244 nm using UV-spectrophotometer.

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data:

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release models.

Zero Order Release Rate Kinetics:

To study the zero-order release kinetics the release rate data are fitted to the following equation.

$$F = K_0 t$$

Where, 'F' is the drug release at time 't', and 'K₀' is the zero order release rate constant. The plot of % drug release versus time is linear.

First Order Release Rate Kinetics:

The release rate data are fitted to the following equation

$$\text{Log}(100-F) = kt$$

A plot of log cumulative percent of drug remaining to be released vs. time is plotted then it gives first order release.

Higuchi Release Model:

To study the Higuchi release kinetics, the release rate data were fitted to the following equation.

$$F = k t^{1/2}$$

Where, 'k' is the Higuchi constant.

In Higuchi model, a plot of % drug release versus square root of time is linear.

Korsmeyer And Peppas Release Model:

The mechanism of drug release was evaluated by plotting the log percentage of drug released versus log time according to Korsmeyer- Peppas equation. The exponent 'n' indicates the mechanism of drug release calculated through the slope of the straight Line.

$$M_t / M_{\infty} = K t^n$$

Where, M_t / M_{∞} is fraction of drug released at time 't', k represents a constant, and 'n' is the diffusional exponent, which characterizes the type of release mechanism during the dissolution process. For non-Fickian release, the value of n falls between 0.5 and 1.0; while in case of Fickian diffusion, n = 0.5; for zero-order release (case I I transport), n=1; and for super case II transport, n > 1. In this model, a plot of log (M_t / M_{∞}) versus log (time) is linear.

Hixson-Crowell Release Model:

$$(100-Q_t)^{1/3} = 100^{1/3} - KHC.t$$

Where, k is the Hixson-Crowell rate constant.

Hixson-Crowell model describes the release of drugs from an insoluble matrix through mainly erosion. (Where there is a change in surface area and diameter of particles or tablets).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The present study was aimed at developing sustained release tablets of Bosentan using various polymers. All the formulations were evaluated for physicochemical properties and in vitro drug release studies.

Analytical Method**Analytical Uv Spectrums Of Bosentan In 0.1N Hcl And 6.8ph Phosphate Buffers:**

Figure 4:UV absorbance spectrum of Bosentan in 0.1N Hcl.

Figure 1:UV absorbance spectrum of Bosentan in 6.8pH buffer.

Graphs of Bosentan were taken in Simulated Gastric fluid (pH 1.2) and in p H 6.8 phosphate buffer at 242 nm and 244 nm respectively.

Table 8: Observations For Graph Of Bosentan In 0.1N Hcl (242 nm)

Conc [$\mu\text{g/ml}$]	Abs
0	0
5	0.104
10	0.205
15	0.302
20	0.411
25	0.503
30	0.608
35	0.710
40	0.808

Figure 2: Standard graph of Bosentan in 0.1N HCl

Table 9: Observations for graph of Bosentan in p H 6.8 phosphate buffer (244 nm)

	Conc [µg/l]	Abs
5		0.098
10		0.195
15		0.298
20		0.392
25		0.490
30		0.595
35		0.690
40		0.776

Figure 3: Standard graph of Bosentan in pH 6.8 phosphate buffer (244 nm)

**Drug And Excipient Compatibility Studies:
FTIR Spectrum Of Pure Drug:**

**Figure 4: FTIR spectrum of pure drug
FTIR Spectrum Of Eudragit RSPO:**

**Figure 5: FTIR spectrum of eudragit RSPO
FTIR Spectrum Of Chitosan:**

**Figure 6: FTIR spectrum of chitosan
FTIR Spectrum Of Optimized Formulation(F3):**

940	1000-650 950-910	=C-H bend O-Bend	Alkenes Carboxylic acids
574,626,684,713, 755,792,842	850-550 690-515	C-Cl stretch C-Br stretch -C#C-H: C-H bend C-H "oop" =C-H bend	Alkyl amides alkyl halides alkynes Aromatics Alkenes
3317,3259,3240,3219 , 3034,3016,2966,2935 , 2872,2742,2596,2839 , 3176,3157,3134,3120 , 3379,3369,3356,3340 , 3471	3500-3200 3400-3250 3330-3270 3100-3000 3100-3000 3000-2850 2830-2695	O-H stretch N-H stretch -C#C-H: C-H stretch C stretch =C-H stretch C stretch H-C=O: C-H stretch	H-bonded alcohols, phenols 10,20 amines, amides Alkyl nes (terminal) Aromatics Alkenes Alkanes Aldehydes
1400	1500-1400	C-C stretch (in-ring)	Aromatics
1251,1172,1112, 1072,1321,1342	1360-1290 1335-1250 1320-1000 1300-1150 1250-1020	AN-Asymmetric stretch C-N stretch C-O stretch C-H wag (-CH ₂ X) C-N stretch	Nitro compounds Aromatic amines Alcohols, carboxylic acids, esters, ethers Alkyl halides Aliphatic amines
711,3434.94, 2927.01, 598.33, 1426.9, 1230, 777.96 680.40	1000-650 910-665 900-675 850-550	=C-H bend N-H wag CH "OOP" C-Cl stretch -OH and NH stretch, -CH ₂ vibration C=O stretch C-O stretch CH ₂ rocking N-Bending	Alkenes 10,20 amines Aromatic Alkyl Halides

Table 11: Preformulation Parameters Of Powder Blend Table 11: Preformulation parameters of Core blend

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose	Bulk density (gm/ml)	Tapped density (gm/ml)	Carr's index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	25.11±0.05	0.49±0.04	0.54±0.04	16.21±0.06	0.86±0.06
F2	25.67±0.02	0.52±0.09	0.52±0.04	16.87±0.05	0.98±0.05

F3	25.54±0.09	0.50±0.05	0.58±0.05	17.11±0.01	0.64±0.03
F4	25.43±0.04	0.51±0.06	0.54±0.07	17.67±0.08	1.12±0.04
F5	25.34±0.05	0.52±0.03	0.57±0.03	16.92±0.04	1.2±0.08
F6	24.22±0.04	0.53±0.04	0.56±0.06	17.65±0.09	1.06±0.09
F7	25.18±0.03	0.54±0.06	0.59±0.04	16.43±0.05	0.76±0.03
F8	24.22±0.08	0.58±0.04	0.67±0.02	17.97±0.02	1.15±0.09
F9	25.05±0.07	0.55±0.08	0.52±0.03	17.54±0.09	1.17±0.02

N=3,±SD standard deviation.

Tablet powder blend was subjected to various preformulation parameters. The angle of repose values indicates that the powder blend has good flow properties. The bulk density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.43±0.07 to 0.58±0.06 (gm/cm³) showing that the powder has good flow properties. The tapped density of all the formulations was found to be in the range of 0.57 to 0.69 showing the powder has good flow properties. The compressibility index of all the formulations was found to be ranging between 16 to 18 which shows

that the powder has good flow properties. All the formulations have shown the hausner ratio ranging between 0 to 1.2 indicating the powder has good flow properties.

Quality Control Parameters For Tablets:

Tablet quality control tests such as weight variation, hardness, and friability, thickness, and drug release studies in different media were performed on the compression coated tablet.

Table 12: post compression parameters of all formulations.

Formulation codes	Weight variation(mg)	Hardness(kg/cm ²)	Friability (%loss)	Thickness (mm)	Drug content (%)
F1	201.5±0.03	4.5±0.03	0.50±0.02	1.8±0.01	99.76±0.058
F2	200.4±0.05	4.5±0.02	0.51±0.05	1.9±0.02	99.45±0.02
F3	199.6±0.03	4.4±0.03	0.51±0.06	1.9±0.01	99.34±0.03
F4	200.6±0.08	4.5±0.04	0.55±0.04	1.9±0.03	99.87±0.04
F5	199.4±0.04	4.4±0.05	0.56±0.08	1.7±0.03	99.14±0.05
F6	200.7±0.02	4.5±0.04	0.45±0.06	1.5±0.02	98.56±0.02
F7	202.3±0.09	4.1±0.05	0.51±0.07	1.4±0.04	98.42±0.08
F8	201.2±0.05	4.3±0.04	0.49±0.06	1.7±0.03	99.65±0.04
F9	199.3±0.06	4.5±0.02	0.55±0.04	1.6±0.01	99.12±0.06

N=3,±SD standard deviation.

Invitro Quality Control Parameters For Tablets

All the parameters such as weight variation, friability, hardness, thickness and drug content were found to be within limits.

***In-Vitro* Drug Release Studies**

Table 13: Dissolution Data of Bosentan Tablets Prepared With Eudragit polymers In Different Concentrations

TIME (hr)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	25.54 ±0.06	20.13 ±0.05	16.43 ±0.04	17.25 ±0.04	16.42 ±0.08	14.62 ±0.05	10.4 ±0.03	9.4 ±0.06	8.5 ±0.08
1	46.73 ±0.03	39.46 ±0.04	26.77 ±0.07	38.26 ±0.06	25.73 ±0.02	19.86 ±0.08	16.5 ±0.08	15.6 ±0.03	14.5 ±0.06
2	76.57 ±0.08	55.38 ±0.02	34.62 ±0.04	54.16 ±0.04	36.63 ±0.06	22.35 ±0.07	28.6 ±0.04	21.4 ±0.08	18.4 ±0.04
3	98.41 ±0.05	75.34 ±0.02	42.45 ±0.07	72.01 ±0.07	45.04 ±0.01	31.45 ±0.05	39.5 ±0.05	36.7 ±0.06	23.4 ±0.08
4		87.36	55.42	88.26 ±0.08	58.25 ±0.08	39.80 ±0.03	48.5	42.4	28.2
		±0.06	±0.03				±0.08	±0.04	±0.06
5		99.43 ±0.04	67.40 ±0.04	97.10 ±0.01	65.33 ±0.05	45.25 ±0.05	59.4 ±0.01	49.6 ±0.06	34.8 ±0.04
6			85.45 ±0.01		76.41 ±0.01	58.24 ±0.04	69.2 ±0.05	55.3 ±0.04	40.2 ±0.07
7			91.54 ±0.08		84.84 ±0.08	66.73 ±0.02	74.5 ±0.08	60.3 ±0.05	44.8 ±0.01
8			98.15 ±0.06		92.80 ±0.04	71.34 ±0.01	82.3 ±0.01	72.8 ±0.05	50.4 ±0.05

N=3,±SD standard deviation.

Figure 8: Dissolution profile of Bosentan (F1, F2, F3 formulations).

Figure 9: Dissolution profile of Bosentan (F4, F5, F6 formulations)

Figure 10: Dissolution profile of Bosentan (F7, F8, F9 formulations)

Release Kinetics:
Kinetic Studies For F3 Formulation

Table 14: Kinetic studies for F3 formulation

CUMULATIVE (%) RELEASE Q	TIME (T)	ROOT (T)	LOG(%) RELEASE	LOG (T)	LOG (%) REMAIN
0	0	0	0	0	2.000
16.43	30	5.477	1.216	1.477	1.922
26.77	60	7.746	1.428	1.778	1.865
34.62	120	10.954	1.539	2.079	1.815
42.45	180	13.416	1.628	2.255	1.760
55.42	240	15.492	1.744	2.380	1.649
67.48	300	17.321	1.829	2.477	1.512
85.45	360	18.974	1.932	2.556	1.163
91.54	420	20.494	1.962	2.623	0.927
98.15	480	21.909	1.992	2.681	0.267

Figure 11:zero order kinetics for F3 formulation.

Figure 12:higuchi graph for F3 formulation

Figure 13:peppas's graph for F3 formulation

Figure 14: first order kinetics for F3 formulation Discussion:

To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the data obtained were graphed as:

- The graph plotted against Percentage drug released and square root of time is the Higuchi's plot and the $R^2=0.951$
- The graph plotted against Log percentage drug remaining and time is the First order kinetics and the $R^2=0.906$
- The graph plotted against Log drug released and log time Peppas plot and the $R^2=0.974$, n value found to be 0.633.
- The graph plotted against cumulative Percentage drug released and time is the zero order kinetics and the $R^2=0.980$.

From observing the above values, it is evident that the optimized formulation(F3) follows the zero order release kinetics.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

The aim of the present study was to develop sustained release formulation of Bosentan to maintain constant therapeutic levels of the drug for over 8 hrs. Various synthetic and natural polymers were employed as polymers. Bosentan dose was fixed as 62.5 mg. Total weight of the tablet was considered as 200 mg. Polymers were used in the concentration of 62.5 and 41.25 mg concentration. All the formulations were passed various physicochemical evaluation parameters and they were found to be within limits. The optimized formulations are checked for the pre and post compression parameters in which the results obtained are optimal for the preparation of formulations. Drug and excipient compatibility studies are also positive showing there is no interaction between the polymers and the drug. Whereas from the dissolution studies it was

evident that the formulation F3 showed better and desired drug release pattern i.e., 98.13 respectively % in 8 hours. From the total work I have performed F3 gave positive results in the preparation of bosentan sustained release tablets whereas the other formulations are unable to retard the drug for the desired time. Stability studies also showed positive results on the drug release of the optimized formulations.

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